

EXPERIMENTS ON RESOLUTION OF CO-ORDINATED
INORGANIC COMPOUNDS INTO OPTICAL ISOMERS.
PART II. CO-ORDINATED ZINC COMPOUNDS
WITH ACTIVE AND RACEMIC PROPYLENE-
DIAMINE.

BY PANCHANAN NEOGI AND KANAI LAL MANDAL.

In this paper complex tripropylenediamine zinc salts have been prepared with three varieties of propylenediamine, *d*, *l* and *r*. Attempts to resolve the racemic compounds have so far not been successful.

Regarding the complex compounds of zinc with *d*- and *l*-propylenediamine, *l*-propylenediamine gave *l*-compounds and *d*-propylenediamine gave *d*-compounds. Similar results have been obtained in the case of complex compounds of cadmium with *d*- and *l*-propylenediamine (Neogi and Mandal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 18, 224).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Zinc tripropylenediamine chloride was obtained by adding 20 g. (70% solution) of propylenediamine in small quantities to a well-cooled solution of anhydrous zinc chloride (10 g.). A white, precipitate which appeared at first, gradually dissolved and a clear solution was obtained. The solution deposited crystals on keeping in a vacuum desiccator for several days. The complex chloride was crystallised from a mixture of equal parts of water and alcohol. It is soluble in water but insoluble in acetone. {Found: N, 23.75; Zn, 18.15. $[\text{Znpn}_3]\text{Cl}_2$ requires N, 23.46; Zn, 18.15 per cent}.

Zinc tripropylenediamine bromide was precipitated from a concentrated solution of zinc tripropylenediamine chloride by adding a solution of potassium bromide. It crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and water. The bromide is less soluble in water than the corresponding chloride. {Found: N 18.53; Zn, 14.39. $[\text{Znpn}_3]\text{Br}_2$ requires N, 18.8; Zn, 14.54 per cent}.

Zinc tripropylenediamine iodide was obtained as a precipitate by adding a saturated solution of potassium iodide to a concentrated solution of zinc tripropylenediamine chloride. It crystallised from a mixture of water and alcohol. The complex iodide is sparingly soluble in water. It is

soluble in acetone. {Found : N, 15'46 ; Zn, 12'4. $[\text{Zn}(\text{npn}_3)] \text{I}_2$ requires N, 15'52; Zn, 12'01 per cent}.

Zinc tripropylenediamine thiocyanate, prepared by the action of potassium thiocyanate on the chloride, was crystallised from a mixture of water and alcohol. {Found : N, 28'1 ; Zn, 16'03. $[\text{Zn}(\text{npn}_3)] (\text{CNS})_2$ requires N, 27'8 ; Zn, 16'13 per cent}.

Zinc tripropylenediamine camphor sulphonate was obtained by adding a solution of the silver salt of camphor sulphonic acid to a solution of zinc tripropylenediamine chloride till silver chloride ceased to be precipitated. The mixture was filtered, and fractionally crystallised in a vacuum desiccator. After prolonged drying in a vacuum desiccator, the first fraction was analysed. {Found : N, 11'14 ; Zn, 8'87. $[\text{Zn}(\text{npn}_3)] (\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{SO}_4)_2$ requires N, 11'2 ; Zn, 8'68 per cent}. Other fractions gave similar analytical results. The value of $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ for the first fraction in a 5% solution in 2 dcm. tube was +22'2°. Other fractions yielded similar rotations. The complex salt obtained after removal of the residue was found to be inactive.

Zinc tripropylenediamine bromocamphor sulphonate.—To a solution of zinc tripropylene chloride, a solution of the silver salt of *d*-bromocamphor sulphonic acid was gradually added till it ceased to give a precipitate. The mixture was filtered and the filtrate evaporated in vacuum and fractionally crystallised. After prolonged drying in a vacuum desiccator, the first fraction was analysed.

{Found : N, 9'48 ; Zn, 7'21. $[\text{Zn}(\text{npn}_3)] (\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{BrSO}_4)_2$ requires N, 9'26 ; Zn, 7'17 per cent}. Other fractions also gave similar analytical results.

The value of $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ for the first fraction was +47°. Other fractions showed similar rotations. The complex salt after removal of the active residue was inactive.

Zinc Tripropylenediamine Tartrate.—A concentrated solution of zinc tripropylenediamine chloride (5 g.) was triturated with silver tartrate (5 g.) and the extract with hot water evaporated in vacuum and fractionally crystallised. After prolonged drying in a vacuum desiccator the first fraction was analysed and its rotation determined. {Found : N, 19'55 ; Zn, 14'66. $[\text{Zn}(\text{npn}_3)] (\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6)$ requires N, 19'31 ; Zn, 14'94 per cent}. Other fractions also gave similar analytical results. A 5% solution gave $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +27'8^\circ$. Other fractions gave similar rotations. The tartrate when converted into the corresponding chloride was found to be inactive.

Zinc l-tri-propylenediamine chloridæ was obtained by combining zinc chloride with *l*-propylenediamine prepared from racemic propylene diamine (cf. Baumann, *Ber.*, 1895, 28, 1179; TSchugaeff, *ibid.*, 1907, 40, 3461;

1909, 42, 55). (Found : N, 23'40 ; Zn, 18'28. Calc. : N, 23'46 ; Zn, 18'15 per cent). 5% solution in water gave $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -48'5$, $[M] = -173'6$.

Zinc l-tripropylenediamine bromide was prepared as the *r*-variety. (Found : N, 18'96 ; Zn, 14'55. Calc. : N, 18'8 ; Zn, 14'54 per cent). 5% solution gave $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +45'$, $[M] = -201'1$.

Zinc l-tripropylenediamine iodide was prepared in the same way as the inactive variety. (Found : N, 15'38 ; Zn, 11'78. Calc. : N, 15'52 ; Zn, 12'01 per cent). 5% solution gave $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -39'2$, $[M] = -212$.

Zinc l-tripropylenediamine thiocyanate was prepared in the same way as the corresponding inactive compound. (Found : N, 27'64 ; Zn, 16'0. Calc. : N, 27'8 ; Zn, 16'13 per cent). 5% solution gave $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -43'7$, $[M] = -176'1$.

Zinc d-tripropylenediamine chloride was prepared from zinc chloride and *d*-propylenediamine (prepared from *r*-variety, *cf.*, Baumann, *loc. cit.*; Tschugaeff, *loc. cit.*). (Found : N, 23'33 ; Zn, 18'31. Calc. : N, 23'46 ; Zn, 18'15 per cent). 5% solution gave $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +44'8$, $[M] = +160'4$.

Zinc d-tripropylenediamine bromide was prepared as the corresponding *l*-bromide. (Found : N, 19'11 ; Zn, 14'35. Calc. : N, 18'8 ; Zn, 14'54 per cent). 5% solution gave $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +44$, $[M] = +196'7$.

Zinc d-tripropylenediamine iodide was prepared as the corresponding *l*-iodide. (Found : N, 15'60 ; Zn, 12'24. Calc. : N, 15'52 ; Zn, 12'01 per cent). 5% solution gave $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +38'6$, $[M] = +208$.

Zinc d-tripropylenediamine thiocyanate was prepared as the *l*-thiocyanate. (Found : N, 27'82 ; Zn, 16'10. Calc. : N, 27'8 ; Zn, 13'13 per cent). 5% solution gave $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +41$, $[M] = +165'2$.